

TRI-AXIAL FAILURE THEORIES FOR FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Attempts have been made in this paper to apply some of the better-known failure criteria for polymer composites to predict the failure of a continuous fibre reinforced/epoxy unidirectional lamina subjected to a triaxial state of stress. The test data, against which these criteria have been assessed, were generated by applying longitudinal tensile and transverse compressive loads to the lamina, in the presence of superposed hydrostatic pressures up to a magnitude of 850MPa. Additional data were also obtained describing the compressive strength behaviour of the epoxy resin.

The interaction coefficients in Tsai's criterion, which were established for 2D stresses, result in conservative predictions when applied to 3D loading situations. The concept employed by Puck's theory, which considers the angle of the action plane under pressure, was observed to be crucial in understanding the pressure dependency of the transverse compressive strength. It is thus concluded that some of the theories developed to predict failure under 2D loading situations can be applied to 3D with some degree of success, but that they require further validation and benchmarking.

Keywords: failure criteria, hydrostatic pressure, triaxial loading, unidirectional, glass/epoxy

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper is concerned with the behaviour of fibre reinforced polymer composites under triaxial states of stress and the theoretical prediction of failure under such situations. Complex stresses are common in many civil and military applications. Examples include structures operating in deep water, the material in and around bolted joints, composite components formed at elevated temperature (and therefore subject to residual stresses) and structures subjected to impact and blast loading.

There is currently a requirement to provide appropriate design data for the suppliers of the raw materials for composite manufacture and more importantly for those concerned with the manufacture of components and structures (the users). The provision of multi-axial test data and failure criteria to cover complex loading cases forms an important part of this design framework. However, generating viable test data, as will be shown later in this introduction, tends to be difficult and expensive. Obviously, the potential benefits arising from the possession of a reliable multi-axial predictive capability are clearly substantial as it minimises or eliminates the need to resorting to the expensive 'make and test' approach, normally adopted in designing composite structures.

Unfortunately, a thorough understanding and accurate prediction of these stresses remain one of the most challenging tasks facing designers for a variety of reasons :-

- Some of the effects observed when testing composites in the through-thickness direction

are not well understood. Composites can exhibit through-thickness compressive strengths that are much larger than the in-plane compressive strength of the same material, while the through-thickness shear strengths are much lower than the in-plane shear strengths, Refs[1-4]. Where the strengths have been unexpectedly high, this has led to possibility of an alternative failure mode coming into play, which then casts doubt on the results.

- Reliable testing methods for generating 3-D stresses, including those in the through-thickness direction, are not generally well established and difficulties are normally encountered in obtaining all the required information from the tests. Consequently, accurate data representing the behaviour of composites under 3-D states of stress are relatively scarce, Refs[5,6]. One of the few experimental sets available are those reported by Hine *et al*, Ref[5] describing the effect of superposed hydrostatic pressure on the mechanical properties of pure epoxy and on the mechanical properties of a unidirectional (UD) E glass/epoxy lamina. Longitudinal tension, transverse compression and 10° off-axis tension tests were carried out on the UD material using coupon specimens, while compression tests were carried out on the resin using circular bars. Strain gauges were used to measure the strains during tests at hydrostatic pressures up to 500MPa. Compression tests on pure epoxy samples showed that the compressive Young’s modulus increases significantly with increasing pressure whilst the compressive strength shows a modest increase with increasing pressure. These experimental results will be subjected to further analysis in this paper.

- As a direct consequence of the above deficiencies, reliable predictive methods, if any exist at all, have not been subjected to thorough benchmarking and remain largely invalidated.

Recently, theories that contain the current, world leading, failure criteria were investigated through the World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE), Ref[7]. Each theory was bench-marked and validated against test data collected under uniaxial and biaxial loading conditions. These covered a large number of loading cases, materials, and lay-ups. A number of these theories were observed to be mature enough to capture various aspects related to biaxial test data, and they are reasonably effective at predicting the mode of failure and final strength and deformation.

Some of these criteria have the potential to be extended to cater for tri-axial states of stress, but no previous attempt has been made to do this. The aim of this paper is take an initial step towards this objective by providing a description of how the current theories deal with the prediction of the data reported by Hine *et al*, Ref[5].

2 Description of the WWFE theories

In the recent ‘World Wide Failure Exercise’, Hinton Kaddour and Soden completed an extensive publication, during 2004, on the benchmarking of some of most widely-used failure criteria for fibre reinforced plastic materials, Ref[7],. Table 1 below lists the name of the originators of the criteria, the approaches they represent and the abbreviated designation of each theory.

Table 1 A summary of participants and approaches represented in the WWFE, Ref[7].

Contributor(s)	Approach represented	Designation
Chamis C C, Gotsis P K and Minnetyan L, Ref[10]	-ICAN (micro-mechanics based) -CODSTRAN	Chamis(1)* Chamis(2)
Hart-Smith L J, Ref[13]	Generalised Tresca theory	Hart-Smith(1)
Hart-Smith L J, Ref[13]	Maximum Strain Theory	Hart-Smith(2)*
Eckold G C, Ref[11]	British Standard pressure vessel design codes	Eckold
Edge E C, Ref[12]	British Aerospace, In-house design method	Edge
McCartney L N, Ref[14]	Physically based ‘Damage Mechanics’	McCartney*

Puck A and Schürmann H, Ref[15]	Physically based 3-D phenomenological models	Puck*
Wolfe W E and Butalia T S, ref[19]	Maximum strain energy method, due to Sandhu	Wolfe
Sun C T and Tao J X, Ref[17]	Linear and FE based nonlinear analysis	Sun(L) Sun(NL)*
Zinoviev P, Grigoriev S V, Labedeva O V and Tairova L, Ref[20]	Development of Maximum stress theory	Zinoviev
Tsai S W and Liu K-S, Ref[18]	Interactive progressive quadratic failure criterion	Tsai*
Rotem A, Ref[16]	Interactive matrix and fibre failure theory	Rotem
Hart-Smith L J, Ref[13]	Ten-Per-Cent rule	Hart-Smith(3)
Cuntze R, Ref[22]	Failure mode concept (FMC)	Cuntze*
Bogetti T, C Hoppel, V Harik, J Newill and B Burns, Ref[21]	3-D Maximum strain	Bogetti*
Mayes S J and A C Hansen, Ref[23]	Multi-continuum micro-mechanics theory	Mayes*
Huang Z-M, Ref[24]	Anisotropic plasticity and generalised max stress	Huang

* Theories already formulated to cater for 3D stresses.

Fig 1 illustrates how the predictions from the various theories compare with experimental measurements for one particular problem, namely the biaxial failure quadrant for a unidirectional

Fig 1 Biaxial failure predictions of the WWFE theories for a unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy lamina when subjected to in-plane longitudinal tension and transverse compression

glass/epoxy material. The measurements were made on hoop wound tubes subjected to internal pressure and compressive end load giving a state of circumferential tension and axial compression. As the tubes were thin, the stress in the third (radial) direction was negligible. It is evident that even for this comparatively simple problem there is wide disagreement between the various theories and that none of them are fully satisfactory for describing the observed behaviour.

Although, the WWFE focussed on two-dimensional (in-plane) stresses, a number of the theories considered have the potential be able to handle failure under three-dimensional stresses. For the purposes of the current paper it has been possible to select some theories that have this potential and also perform reasonably well with 2D problems of the type shown above. The representative theories are those including Puck, Cuntze, Tsai, Chamis, Bogetti, Zinoviev and Hart-Smith. Full descriptions of each of these theories can be found in Ref[7].

3 Comparison with data

The test data used in the present work is that published by Hine *et al*, Ref [5]. The materials used were E-glass fibres and an MY750/HY917/DY070 epoxy resin system. The tests were carried out in three configurations with hydrostatic pressure superimposed in each case; (1) longitudinal tension in the fibre direction, (2) transverse compression across the fibres and (3) compression of the unreinforced matrix. The loading was achieved by first applying pressure around the specimen and then either applying extra tensile load in the fibre direction for (1), extra transverse compressive load across the fibres for (2) and compression of the matrix for (3). The results are presented in Figs 2, 3 and 5 in two forms. The first form, shown by the empty circles, describes the total stress (which includes the hydrostatic component). The second form, shown by the solid squares, describes the stress component that excludes the hydrostatic pressure component.

3.1 Longitudinal tensile strength

Fig 2 shows a comparison between test data and a number of failure theories of the variation of longitudinal tensile strength with pressure. The test data indicates an overall decrease in the

Fig 2 Comparison between some WWFE theories and test data for effect of pressure on the longitudinal tensile strength of unidirectional glass/epoxy lamina

strength with increasing pressure. As the pressure approaches 850MPa, the specimens could carry almost no longitudinal tensile strength.

Although the test data are somewhat sparse it is readily apparent that certain of the theories may contain significant deficiencies in their formulation, given the gross underestimation of the effect of the hydrostatic component.

One of the essential requirements to employing Tsai's theory is the determination of the interaction coefficients K_{12} , K_{13} and K_{23} . For two-dimensional problems, such as those provided in the WWFE, Tsai suggested that the coefficient K_{12} be set at -0.5 . The use of Tsai's theory based on these values is referred to in this paper as Tsai(1). This predicts a closed envelope where the lamina cannot carry any longitudinal tension at pressures above 340MPa.

Because of its apparent versatility, due to the incorporation of all the 3-D strength values in one equation, attempts have been made by a few investigators to apply this equation to 3-D stress states. In Ref[6], Tsai's theory was used to predict the effect of pressure on the longitudinal and transverse strength of Kevlar/epoxy lamina. The interaction terms K_{12} (and K_{13}) and K_{23} were obtained from fitting the above equation to some of the test data. The results of the best fit gave the following values $K_{12}=K_{13}=K_{23}/25.8= -0.026$. The predictions of Tsai's theory based on these values are referred to as Tsai(2).

It is perhaps worth pointing out that alternative values for the interaction terms were obtained by other investigators. DeTeresa and Larsen, Ref[8], attempted to reduce the number of coefficients in Tsai's theory for applications under 3-D stresses by making assumptions including that composite materials do not fail under practical levels of either hydrostatic pressure or under equal transverse and through-thickness compressive stresses. The resulting coefficients were $F_{12}=F_{11}/4$, $F_{23}=F_{22}$, which are obviously different to those suggested in the above sections.

Some extreme limits were obtained from Puck, maximum stress and maximum strain theories. Puck's theory, employed for $p_{\perp}^{(-)}=0.25$, gave a maximum pressure 116MPa, a value less than the transverse compressive strength at atmospheric pressure. By its non-interactive nature, Zinoviev's theory is limited to a pressure of -145MPa. The maximum strain theory seems to predict favourably the trend in the strength only when the hydrostatic pressure component is deducted from the measured stress. The theory predicts the lamina to carry no longitudinal tension at a pressure of around 2300MPa, as apposed to around 900MPa observed in the experiments.

The prediction of Cuntze's theory gave a large variety of options, depending upon the empirical parameters employed, including the mode interaction coefficient m and b_{\perp}^{τ} . For $b_{\perp}^{\tau}=1$, and regardless of the value of m , there will be no effect of pressure on the strength. In order to demonstrate the extreme prediction of the theory, a curve is shown which represents the maximum value suggested by Cuntze, i.e. for $b_{\perp}^{\tau}=1.2$. The prediction suggests that the composite would not be able to carry tension load along the fibres beyond 365MPa pressure. However, based on a personal communication with Cuntze, it was suggested that, for the case of longitudinal tension and transverse and through-thickness pressure, the FF1 and IFF3 modes of failure should be replaced with Poisson's ratio effects. Thus, Cuntze's theory aligns itself with that camp advocating the use of the maximum strain theory.

An aspect of the behaviour of the material that was reported in Ref[5] is the change in mode of failure at large pressure. Fig 3 shows a picture of fractured specimens tested under two

pressures. The brush-like and fibre splitting behaviour observed at atmospheric pressure was

Fig 3 Failed specimens tested under different pressures. Top: at 0.1MPa and the bottom at 500MPa

changed into a clean cut perpendicular to the fibre direction. Similar behaviour was reported in Ref[6] when testing hoop wound rings under various pressure. It is possible that an application of hydrostatic pressure would enhance the interfacial shear strength between fibres and matrix, leading to overcoming

the splitting behaviour, observed in the tests. However, the criteria used in WWFE do not appear to be able to predict that change in mode of failure and the issue remained largely unresolved.

3.2 Compression of epoxy matrix

Fig 4 shows a comparison between test data and a number of failure theories of the variation of compressive strength with pressure for the epoxy resin. The test data indicates a large increase

Fig 4 Comparison between theories and test data for the resin compressive strength

in the strength with increasing pressure. A straight line representing the ‘true’ or ‘pure’ hydrostatic pressure loading ($\sigma_1=\sigma_2=\sigma_3= P$) is drawn in Fig 4. It is clear from the test data that failure does not take place under pure hydrostatic pressure for the values shown in the figure. Both Chamis and Tsai(1) theories predicted open envelopes, indicated by two curves parallel to that of the pure hydrostatic pressure, with a good correlation with the measured data. Although the maximum strain theory gives an accurate trend, it underestimated the strength whilst the deviation between the prediction and the test data increased with increasing pressure. The

remaining theories gave very conservative predictions.

3.3 Transverse compression strength

Fig 5 shows a comparison between the prediction of some theories and the test data. The experimental results show that the transverse compressive strength (with and without the inclusion of the hydrostatic pressure component) increases with increasing the pressure. Although the test data exhibited some problems at low pressure, with the measured atmospheric

Fig 5 Comparison between some of the WWFE theories and test data for transverse compressive strength of glass/epoxy lamina

pressure being lower than that reported in Ref[5] for the same material, the correlation between the experimental data and the theories seems to be acceptable for Puck's and Cuntze's theories.

The correlation between the maximum strain theory and test data should be viewed with a high degree of caution as transverse failure strain can increase with increasing pressure and this was not considered in the predictions in Fig 5. The other theories did not accurately capture the trend observed in the tests. For example, the test data show a continuous increase in the strength with increasing pressure, Tsai (1), Tsai(2) and Zinoviev's theories predicted closed envelopes with pressure not exceeding a certain limit.

The curves shown for Cuntze's theory represent the modified IFF3 mode of failure, together with allowance made for the interaction between IFF3 and FF2. However, based on a personal communication with Cuntze, Ref[25], it was suggested that, despite what the equations stated, there is no fracture under a full hydrostatic pressure. Similar views were expressed previously in Refs[6,8]. However, it was noted that the experimental data in Ref[6] covered pressure values only up to 300MPa and hence one could argue about the lack of experimental evidence to

substantiate the claim made.

For sake of argument, a line representing the ‘true’ or ‘pure’ hydrostatic pressure loading ($\sigma_1=\sigma_2=\sigma_3= P$) is drawn in Fig 5. It is clear that the experimental results, as well as the Inter Fibre Failure IFF modes of Puck and Cuntze, support the previous observations that no failure takes place under ‘pure’ hydrostatic pressure but this was true only up to a certain pressure, being either equal to or just below the maximum recorded pressure of 850MPa. Hence the predictive capabilities of these two theories at pressures above 850MPa remain unchallenged due to a lack of test data in that regime. The other theories (Tsai, Chamis, Maximum strain etc..) show that failure takes place for a loading corresponding to pure hydrostatic pressure.

It is worth noting here that the test data were obtained by firstly applying the pressure (following the pure hydrostatic pressure line), and then a compression load was applied in the transverse direction.

Fig 6: Failed specimens tested under transverse compression

It is probably too early to conclude any load-path dependency effects on the failure strength. Recent work by the authors, Ref[27], shows that the loading path under triaxial compression of thick and large composite tubes made no difference to the failure strength of thick composite tubes for moderate pressure values, less than 150MPa.

The modes of failure of samples tested at different pressures are shown in Fig 6. Almost all of the specimens failed by shear on a plane at $\sim 50^\circ$ to the side face. This mode of failure, at atmospheric pressures, has been commonly observed in most unidirectional composites under transverse compression, e.g. Refs[9,26]. In fact, phenomenological failure theories, such as that of Puck, can predict the angle of action plane (fracture surface).

The fracture surface, for the relatively small number of tests reported in Ref[5], under various pressures seems to exhibit little or no change, although it was difficult to accurately measure the angle due to the occasional rugged nature of these surfaces, and the large increase in the failure strains, Ref[5]. The prediction of the angle of fracture surface, using Puck’s theory, as a function of pressure has not been carried out in the present work for combined transverse compressive and through thickness compression. The results show that, at atmospheric pressure, the angle of fracture is computed as $(\theta)=50.76^\circ$, see Fig 7, and this is obtained for $p_{\perp}^{(-)}=0.25$. As the through-thickness stress increases, the angle decreases. For a stress ratio equals 1 ($\sigma_3=\sigma_2$), the theory predicts no dependency of failure on the action plane angle. As the through-thickness stress exceeds the transverse stress, the angle decreases below 45° .

Fig 7 Effect of stress ratio on the angle of action plane

For the stress ratios (σ_3/σ_2) achieved in the tests, being $0 < (\sigma_3/\sigma_2) < 0.66$, the fracture angle is predicted by Puck's theory to decrease by about 3° only. This may explain why no drastic change in the fracture angle was observed in the tests.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- For designers seeking to predict the modes of deformation and ultimate strength under 3D loading conditions, this paper gives an initial assessment as to which theories are likely to be the most successful and the likely level of confidence in the predictions. Furthermore this paper has taken an encouraging first step towards generating improved predictive tools for 3D stress conditions and has made comparisons with measured data covering a range of practically important loading cases.
- There remains a need for more good quality measurements on the behaviour of composites when tested to destruction under superimposed hydrostatic pressure.
- Some of the theories previously examined through the WWFE perform well in predicting behaviour under 2-D stresses and furthermore have the potential to be extended to deal with 3-D stress states. However, these extended theories require further validation and benchmarking.
- When neglecting the pressure dependency on failure strains and the hydrostatic stress component, theories that contain variants of the maximum strain criteria (eg Bogetti or Hart-Smith), seem to capture the general trend observed in the test data.
- The interaction coefficients in Tsai's criterion, which were established for 2-D stress analysis, are not suitable for carrying out 3-D stress analysis as they result in conservative predictions.

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